

Data Management Plan for project "Model-Based Methodology for Development of IT Project Management Plan and Scope Using Artificial Intelligence Algorithms"

Version 1

Description

The project develops a model-driven and AI-assisted methodology for automated generation of IT project scope and project management plan artefacts. The DMP covers conceptual models, transformation outputs, structured artefact pools (JSON), backlog datasets, scope artefacts, project plan documents, and Systematic Literature Review (SLR) datasets associated with the research.

The project includes two Systematic Literature Review (SLR) datasets that were developed to analyse existing approaches to artefact transformation, model-driven engineering applications, and AI-assisted techniques in early IT project management phases. These datasets contain structured metadata extracted from peer-reviewed scientific publications, including bibliographic information, methodological classifications, artefact types, transformation relationships, automation levels, and identified research gaps. The SLR datasets were constructed following PRISMA review protocols, including transparent search strategies, inclusion and exclusion criteria, screening procedures, and structured data extraction.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science

Grant

Model-Based Methodology for
Development of IT Project
Management Plan and Scope
Development using Artificial
Intellect Algorithms

Researchers

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Organizations

Riga Technical University

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: Data Management Plan for project "Model-Based Methodology for Development of IT Project Management Plan and Scope Using Artificial Intelligence Algorithms"

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Organizations:

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: Latvian Council of Science

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Grants: Model-Based Methodology for Development of IT Project Management Plan and Scope Development using Artificial Intellect Algorithms

Project:

3. License

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Access Rights: Public

Publication Date: 2026-01-31

4. Templates

Descriptions

LCS FARP

The table contains data of Systematic Literature Review. An initial literature pool is constructed by examining Scopus, IEEE, ACM, ScienceDirect, IEEExplore databases of scientific papers. Firstly, the pool is filtered by reviewing study titles and abstracts. Secondly, a full-text assessment is performed for each remaining study to identify its relevance to the research scope. Subsequently, a snowballing technique is applied to identify additional relevant studies that may have been missed due to not being found with the search query. The following criteria are applied to select the initial pool of studies:

- Year of publication: 2020–2024.
- Language: English.
- Subject area: Computer science.

To identify potentially relevant studies, the following keywords are listed in a search query:

("software" OR "information system") AND ("software development" OR "software project management") AND ("software requirement specification" OR "user story" OR "user stories") AND ("scrum" OR "kanban" OR "waterfall" OR "iterative" OR "incremental").

The initial search yields 304 studies on Scopus, combined with duplicates excluded from paper sets found on IEEE, ACM, ScienceDirect, IEEExplore databases.

A manual screening process identified 80 relevant studies with transformations within the research scope.

18 studies published in 2020, 16 - 2021, 19 - 2022, 15 - 2023, 12 - 2024.

Consequently, all the artefacts, notations used for that artefacts and their types described in the selected 80 papers are registered in the spreadsheet.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The primary objective of this systematic mapping study research is to identify existing research on artefacts used for IT project management at the initial stages before the software implementation.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Survey data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

XLS

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

65

KB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The data may be useful for researchers working in the area of model-driven development.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

No

This is a simple collection of literature survey data with no metadata.

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

No

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

No

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

Embargo period till 30 June 2025. We are planning to publish paper summarizing the analysis of the data collected. After paper publication acceptance the access will be available.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

No

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Microsoft Excel

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

The data are given as .xls file which can be read by any programming language as a data set to update.

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

CC BY-NC

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

While data are actual as far as they contain Literature Survey on papers published in 2020-2025 under CC BY-NC

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2026-01-31

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2030-01-31

While data are actual as far as they contain Literature Survey on papers published in 2020-2025 under CC BY-NC

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

The expenses will be covered from project budget

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Oksana Nikiforova (0000-0001-7983-3088)

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Passwords

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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